

Damage to rice varieties infected with BPH in a free-choice test, and BPH fecundity, egg hatchability, nymph growth and development, and Population increase on 10 rice varieties with different genes for resistance.^a Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Resistance gene	Damage rating	Fecundity (no. eggs/female)	Hatchability (%) ^b	Nymphs becoming ^c	Development (d) adults	Growth index (%)	Population increase (no./cage)
IR747-B2-6	<i>Bph 1</i>	9.0 a	525 c	93 e	94 d	12.7 a	1.4 d	512 c
Mudgo	<i>Bph 1</i>	5.4 b	290 b	62 d	62 c	13.4 b	4.6 c	270 b
ASD7	<i>bph 2</i>	9.0 a	537 c	94 e	94 d	12.7 a	7.4 d	515 c
Ptb 18	<i>bph 2</i>	5.8 b	298 b	63 d	64 c	13.3 b	4.8 c	275 b
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph 3</i>	1.0 c	122 a	46 bc	44 ab	14.9 c	2.9 ab	99 a
Babawee	<i>bph 4</i>	1.0 c	123 a	46 bc	40 ab	14.7 c	2.7 ab	106 a
ARC10550	<i>bph 5</i>	1.4 c	121 a	48 c	46 b	14.8 c	3.1 b	100 a
Swarnalata	<i>Bph 6</i>	1.0 c	116 a	44 ab	42 ab	14.9 c	2.8 ab	103 a
Ptb 33	<i>bph 2 + Bph 3</i>	1.0 c	118 a	41 a	38 a	15.1 d	2.5 a	101 a
TN1	(no resistance gene)	9.0 a	535 c	93 e	96 d	12.6 a	7.6 d	515 c

^aAv of 5 replications. Separation of means in a column by DMRT at the 5% level. ^bThree newly emerged males and females were caged on 30-d-old plants. ^cTen newly emerged 1st-instar nymphs caged on 30-d-old plants.

Rathu Heenati, Babawee, ARC10550, Swarnalata, and Ptb 33. Significantly more nymphs became adults on susceptible TN1, IR747-B2-6, and ASD7. Nymph development was delayed and growth indices were lower on moderately resistant and resistant varieties. The population increase was 2-

4 times higher on TN1, IR747-B2-6, and ASD7 than on Rathu Heenati, Babawee, ARC10550, Swarnalata, and Ptb 33.

Evidently, *Bph 1* and *bph 2* genes do not confer resistance against the BPH population in Tamil Nadu. Minor genes

probably contribute to a moderate level of resistance in monogenic varieties Mudgo (*Bph 1*) and Ptb 18 (*bph 2*). Varieties with *Bph 3*, *bph 4*, *bph 5*, *Bph 6*, and *bph 2 + Bph 3* genes had high levels of resistance to the BPH population in Tamil Nadu. □

Mass-rearing of rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* Olivier and testing of BR varieties for resistance

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We developed a simple technique to rear rice hispa in the greenhouse. The mass-reared insects were used to test resistance of 15 BRRI rice varieties.

Hispa beetles were collected from ricefields, sorted by sex, and released on potted 30-d-old BR3 rice plants inside 1.8- × 0.6- × 0.6-m fine-mesh wire cages for oviposition. After 34 d, plants with eggs were transferred to another cage for development of grubs. Grubs developing in the leaves were easily visible. Plants were sprinkled with water intermittently during daytime by means of a fine sprinkler until most grubs approached the pupal stage.

Grubs usually developed in 2 wk and turned brownish at pupation. Plants with pupae were transferred to another

Diagram for mass-rearing of hispa on rice plants. BRRI.

cage for adult emergence (34 d). For mating, emerged beetles were confined in another cage with healthy plants 1 wk.

Four to five mated pairs per pot were released on 30-d-old plants in the egg-laying cage (see figure) for 3-4 d. The cycle was repeated to obtain hispa beetles of about the same age.

With limited facilities, we were able to obtain 80% grub survival and rear 400-600 beetles in each hatch. Each generation took about 4 wk. Hispa

grubs required high amount of moisture for development. Egg hatching and grub survival were greatly affected if the plants were not sprinkled with water. Egg deposition and grub survival were more satisfactory on 30- to 40-d-old plants.

To determine varietal reactions, one seedling each of 15 BR varieties (BR1 to BR16, except BR13) and susceptible check TN1 were planted at random in a 60- × 40- × 10-cm wooden seedbox at

10-cm spacing, with 3 seedboxes as replications. When plants were 30 d old, each seedbox was covered with a rectangular fine-mesh wire cage on a water-filled tray and infested with 3 greenhouse-reared hispa beetles per plant. Leaf damage was graded 7 d after infestation, when TN1 plants had more than 50% leaf damage.

All test varieties had high damage, indicating susceptibility to hispa beetles. □

Evaluation of rice germplasm against rice leaffolder (LF) in the greenhouse

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We developed a method to identify *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) resistance donors in the greenhouse. The test is based on scraping of leaf chlorophyll by larvae.

One 5th-instar larva was caged on each 45-d-old plant (5 plants/ test variety) for 48 h. Leaf area damage was measured by placing the leaf on mm² graph paper on a light table and

Rice varieties registering low leaf area damage from rice LF *C. medinalis* in the greenhouse. Hyderabad, India.

Variety	Damaged leaf area (mm ²)
Choorapundy	71.0
Gorsa	94.6
Ptb 33	113.8
Ptb 19	118.3
T10	125.0
ARC10660	129.4
Kula Peruvela	148.2
Balam	151.2
Chempan	151.2
ET5742	167.4
W1263	167.5
Chemban	170.4
Co 29	172.0
Darukasail	181.8
ARC7064	187.0
MO I	189.6
T1406	191.8
Ptb 12 (resistant check)	161.3
TN1 (susceptible check)	326.0

counting the squares visible through the translucent damaged area. Damaged area averaged 326 mm² for susceptible check TN1 and 161.3 mm² for resistant check Ptb 12.

We evaluated more than 100 rice lines using this method. The lowest leaf

damage was 71 mm² in Choorapundy, the highest was 403 mm² in Company Chittari. The table lists rice varieties with less than 200 mm² damage. They can be rated as resistant to moderately resistant. □

Adverse temperature tolerance

Screening for cold tolerance in Burundi

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Rice has been cultivated for many centuries by Baswahili populations along Lake Tanganyika, in swampy areas (780 m) or in upland areas from lake level to 1,300 m. The typical upland rices are called Pandabilima (that which escapes toward the mountain) in Swahili.

Sterility induced by low temperatures in Burundi.

Variety	Origin	Sterility (%)
B2978b-Sr2-6-2-2	Indonesia	37.4
B2980b-Sr2-6-2-3-2	Indonesia	45.1
B2982b-Sr62-3-1-4	Indonesia	63.9
B2983b-Sr85-3-2-4	Indonesia	65.2
Barkat (K78-13)	Bangladesh	32.3
Br51-315-2B-39-1-1	Bangladesh	97.2
Br220-1-1	Bangladesh	95.1

Table continued

Variety	Origin	Sterility (%)
Br319-1	Bangladesh	100
Chan Wang Ku (1539)	China	88.7
IR2061-522-6-9	IRRI	83.4
IR5716-18-1	IRRI	75.2
IR7167-33-2-3-3-1	IRRI	78.1
IR9202-6-1-1	IRRI	72.1
IR9202-33-4-2-1	IRRI	70.9
IR13155-60-3-1-2-1	IRRI	80.6
IR15579-85-2-3	IRRI	92.7
IR15579-135-3	IRRI	69.3
IR15889-32-1	IRRI	67.7
IR18476-55-2	IRRI	67.5
IR22723-RR-4-2	IRRI	70.7
IR22623-RR-4-3	IRRI	81.6
IR24312-RR-19-3-B	IRRI	83.2
K288	India	82.6
K438	India	49.0
K443-106	India	87.0
Kaohsiung Sen Yu 252	Taiwan	87.2
NR10041-66-3-1	Nepal	70.8
RP1848-54-2-3-1	India	77.7
RP1848-109-2-1-1	India	66.2
RP1931-68-4-1-2	India	90.0
Se Lin R (4767)	Proc.	97.6
Shoa Nan Tsan	Proc.	79.7
Stejarree 45	USSR	32.2
Swat I	Pakistan	74.7
YR1641-GH12-5-1GH4	Korea	90.2
YR2379-47-2	Korea	93.7
Yunnan 3	China	12.9